

Draft email template for contacting contributing authors (tailored to suit emailer)

My name is NAME and I am writing to you as a Coordinating Lead Author for chapter 1 of the **new assessment being performed by IPBES (the Intergovernmental Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services) on the topic of transformative change.**

The transformative change assessment was approved by the IPBES plenary in 2021 and will be based on the scoping document (available: <https://ipbes.net/transformative-change>). Transformative change has been broadly defined as fundamental changes across technological, economic and social factors, including paradigms, goals and values, needed to address interlinked sustainability crises and ensure long-term human well-being and flourishing life on a biodiverse planet.

Contributing authors to IPBES assessments are individuals identified as having expertise of particular relevance to the assessment. When invited to be involved in the assessment, Contributing Authors are requested to provide targeted contributions for a particular section of the document.

As part of our work, chapter 1 will assess how transformative change is conceptualised and approached across different communities. After an initial scoping, we have **identified you as a relevant expert within the field of ecological justice and multispecies perspectives**, with the ability to describe important aspects and insights from this field for understanding and approaching transformative change.

I am therefore writing to **ask if you would be willing to contribute to chapter 1 of this IPBES assessment by submitting a 1000 word description of how work in this field views the need for / concept of transformative change, including elements and dimensions it emphasises as important.**

This text should **include citations of 20-30 key references** (peer-reviewed publications, grey literature etc), which the chapter authors will then analyse further. If you choose to share any indigenous and local knowledge or materials, it is important to confirm that you are authorised to share this information and that it is non-confidential. Please note that the assessment is operating according to a tight timeframe, which means we would **ideally like to receive this brief text by July 17th.**

Contributing authors are acknowledged on the first page of the chapter to which they have contributed but only authors nominated through the authors formal nomination process for IPBES assessments will appear in the citation of the chapter. The IPBES author team also has an explicit intention to publish this part of the chapter as a separate review article, for which you will be invited as a co-author.

It is important to note that the confidentiality rules of IPBES do not allow Contributing Authors to have access to the entire assessment document, the shared folder or drafts of the full chapter. Contributions by contributing authors may inform the research process and following review rounds may or may not end up in the final product. It is therefore important to note that by contributing to the assessment you consent to the following:

- *The final assessment text may not include your contributions at all*
- *The final assessment text may not include your contributions in full*
- *The final assessment may include a highly edited or synthesised version of your contributions*
- *Your full contribution may be made publicly available in a data management report or in supplementary materials*

We hope that you are willing to contribute your knowledge to this important international effort and if you have any further questions about the process or request before you can accept or decline this invitation, please just let me know.

With thanks and best wishes,